

Speculation on Newton's Second Law In Terms of Information

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Historically Newtonian mechanics appeared before the statistical mechanical treatment of a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas. In this note, however, we initially investigate a MB gas in terms of information which we define as $-\ln(\text{density}(x))$. In equilibrium there are no macroscopic changes in time so there is only one variable namely x in one dimension. The density may be changed so it is variable while a potential $V(x)$ is not. Thus we argue that there should be a fixed piece of information based on x in the system i.e. $V(x)$. We then argue (as in (1)) that equilibrium involves minimizing the information so we suggest: $-\ln(\text{density}(x)) = C V(x)$. This ultimately leads to the form $d(x) = C_1 \exp(-V(x)/T)$.

Next we focus on a Newtonian system, but unlike the MB gas two variables x and t are needed to describe the macroscopic changes for the particle even though x suffices to describe $V(x)$. {In particular one may send in a particle with an initial speed at x_0 and it will move through x, t in a certain manner. Sending another particle with the same initial speed at x_0 at a later time leads to the same motion. Thus we argue there is a given $V(x)$ function in the system. } We also suggest there should exist a density $d(x)$ and an information given by $-\ln(d(x))$. One may see from (2) that a Newtonian system may be described by a $\text{density}(x)$ even though it is usually only described by $x(t)$, velocity, acceleration etc. The density is linked to a variable quantity of "information" in the system. Given the presence of $V(x)$ we divide the x axis into equally spaced dx units. Thus d/dx the translation generator applies to $V(x)$. For the moving object, however, one has a corresponding $dt(x)$ for each equal dx and the dt 's are usually not the same. In other words the ratio $dx/dt = \text{function}(x)$, but it is dt which changes. We place dt in the denominator so that it mimics the time translational generator d/dt .

One cannot simply equate $\text{function}(x)$ and $C V(x)$ because $\text{function}(x)$ does not change as d/dx , rather it changes because dt values change. Thus we suggest using d/dt to express its changes. As a result we propose: $d/dt (dx/dt) = C dV/dx$ ((1)) as both sides of the equation must be vectors. Now $d/dt = dx/dt d/dx$ so both sides of ((1)) may be expressed as functions of x . One then obtains $\text{function}(x) d/dx \text{function}(x) = C dV/dx$ where $\text{function}(x) = dx/dt$. We call this $v(x)$. $v(x)$ is adjustable so we equate it with information i.e. $-\ln(d(x))$ where $d(x)$ is density as there is no reason to have two different functions of x . Thus $d(x) = C/v(x)$. In other words $\text{density}(x)$ is proportional to the "information" dt at each x . In (2) a density is ascribed to a Newtonian system using dt as the definition of density. Here we wish to link density to $\text{information} = -\ln(d(x))$.

As a result one finds that ((1)) involves information squared unlike the MB gas which involves information $-\ln(d(x))$ to the first power. As a result: $d/dx (v(x)v(x)) = C dV/dx$ which may be integrated to yield Newton's conservation of energy: $.5v(x)v(x) + C V(x) = \text{constant}$. In other words we suggest it may be possible to obtain Newton's second law using ideas of information. There is further loss of information as the constant applies to all x points so the the information from $.5v(x)v(x)$ combines with $CV(x)$ to eliminate x information. (x information, however, is present in each term i.e. $.5v(x)v(x)$ and $CV(x)$).

Information in a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Gas

An MB gas is interesting because it produces a macroscopically static equilibrium scenario with a spatial density due to a potential $V(x)$. A microscopic particle, however, is not static. It is involved in two types of interactions: (A) two body collisions with other gas particles or wall particles and (B) interactions with $V(x)$ which accelerate it. Thus such a single particle may change its momentum in two ways. If one focuses on information then density(x) carries x information and seems to be linked directly to $V(x)$. In this problem $KE(x) = CT d(x)$ where C is a constant and T is related to thermal energy. We argued in (1) that equilibrium tries to minimize information. We call $-\ln(d(x))$ information so that first order changes (e.g. d/dx) are expressed in relative terms i.e. $-d d(x)/dx / d(x)$. Thus we argue that given $V(x)$ as unchangeable information, $d(x)$ may change so that it does not represent any new information i.e. $-\ln(d(x)) = C_2 V(x)$ where C_2 is a constant. This is possible because the kinetic energy $CTd(x)$ is not involved in any new constraint with $V(x)$. In other words T temperature is a given constant and $d(x)$ may change without affecting it. Thus we argue as in (1) that:

density(x) = $d(x) = \exp(-C_2 V(x))$ ((2)) using strictly arguments related to information.

Furthermore no mention of the constituent gas particles has been made in obtaining ((2)). It seems, however, that there are more informational type ideas present. From Newtonian mechanics a single particle accelerates within a $V(x)$. This picture, however, requires two variables x and t, but an equilibrium MB gas only requires one, namely x. Thus all information of t is lost. Thus KE average(x) must be linked to a static quantity, namely density(x). It cannot be linked to a say a $v_{rms}(x)$ as in the time-independent Schrodinger equation where:

KE average(x) = $.5m v_{rms}(x) v_{rms}(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ where W =wavefunction ((3))

As a result, in an MB gas there must be interactions other than with $V(x)$ that allow for: $KE_{average}(x) = \text{constant} * d(x)$. These interactions must affect constituent particles which have $.5mv(x)v(x)$ values which change with x in a manner which keeps track of x,t as long as the second interaction does not act. The second interaction is due to two body constituent particle collisions. These are not linked to $V(x)$ at a point x in the sense that at any given x: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$ where $n(e_1)$ is the number of e_1 particles at x and $e_1 = .5mv(x)v(x)$ at x. For a single particle in a Newtonian picture with only $V(x)$ there is a spatial invariance due to $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. For $V(x)=0$ $n(e_1) = C_3 \exp(-e_1/T)$. A single particle also has $V(x)$ and so its E is indistinguishable at any x, thus one might expect its probability to also be indistinguishable. This leads to $n(e,x) = C \exp(- [.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x)]/T)$. This is in keeping with $d(x) = C_3 \exp(-V(x)/T)$.

Information For a Newtonian Particle in a V(x)

We ask: How does one apply ideas of information to a Newtonian particle in a potential $V(x)$? In such a picture, as noted above, one must have two variables x and t. One cannot describe

the particle's motion with only one because this is not a static problem. $V(x)$, however, is static and one may consider it together with an x axis divided into equally spaced dx units. Each dx unit then must be linked to a different dt value. Thus $dt(x)$ and $dx/dt = \text{function}(x)$. We place dt in the denominator so that it is consistent with the time displacement operator d/dt .

For an MB gas one introduces a spatial density $d(x)$ linked to $V(x)$ so one should also consider a density (x) in the Newtonian problem due to the presence of $V(x)$. For the MB gas one immediately links $-\ln(d(x))$ to $C V(x)$. Why cannot this be done for the Newtonian case? For the MB case the problem is static so using the translational operator d/dx one may move from one dx to another in an equal sense because there is no extra variable time. In the Newtonian case there is an extra variable time and one cannot move equally from one dx to another when describing the particle (although this may be done for $V(x)$). Thus d/dx does not describe properly how a particle moves from one dx to another. Rather for dx constant and $dt(x)$, a change from one dx to another is linked with d/dt as the generator of change. Thus we suggest:

$$-d/dt \ln(d(x)) = C dV/dx \quad ((3))$$

Why is dV/dx instead of $V(x)$ used? We argue that because one is forced to use d/dt to describe changes as one moves from one dx to another this represents a vector and so one must consider changes in $V(x)$ as it moves from one dx to another i.e. create a vector. $V(x)$ only depends on x as it is static.

The next step is to consider $d/dt = dx/dt d/dx = \text{function}(x) d/dx$. As a result one has a weighted spatial displacement.

Then ((3)) becomes:

$$-\text{function}(x) d/dx \ln(d(x)) = C dV/dx \quad ((4))$$

Given that $d(x)$ and $\text{function}(x)$ may both vary whereas $V(x)$ is a fixed function and that equilibrium behaviour should minimize information, we suggest that:

$$-\ln(d(x)) = \text{function}(x) \quad ((5))$$

Otherwise there would be two different functions in the picture namely $-\ln(d(x))$ and $\text{function}(x)$ which represents extra information. There would need to be an extra condition to define these two and that does not seem to exist. One might ask why one doesn't assign $d(x) = \text{function}(x)$, but that would assume $g(x) = -\ln(d(x))$ and the existence of a rule that suggested $\exp(-g(x))$ and not $g(x)$ should be linked with $\text{function}(x)$.

We note that one does not usually think of a Newtonian problem as being associated with a spatial density $d(x)$. Instead one thinks of $x(t)$, $v(x)$, acceleration etc. In (2), however, a spatial density $C/v(x)$ is associated with each x point. This density is proportional to $dt(x)$ i.e. the amount of time a particle spends in each constant dx spatial unit.

Thus:

$\text{function}(x) d/dx \text{function}(x) = C dV/dx$, but $\text{function}(x) = dx/dt$ If one calls $dx/dt = v(x)$ then:

$$v(x) \frac{d}{dx} v(x) = C \frac{dV}{dx} \quad \text{or} \quad .5 v(x)v(x) - C V(x) = \text{constant} \quad ((6))$$

((6)) represents Newton's second law and its equivalent conservation of energy form.

Thus we argue that one may obtain Newton's second law strictly from informational arguments. We also point out that an extra piece of information is lost in equilibrium in the following way. $V(x)$ is a given function which depends on x . ((6)) shows, however, that a function $.5v(x)v(x)$ where $dx/dt = v(x)$ arranges itself such that overall all spatial information at x is lost i.e. $.5v(x)v(x) - CV(x) = \text{constant}$.

Conclusion

In conclusion we investigate whether one may describe Newton's second law and its conservation of energy form in terms of information which we define as $-\ln(\text{density}(x))$ where $\text{density}(x) = \text{spatial density}$. Usually one does not think of a Newtonian problem as having a spatial density. One only thinks in terms of $x(t)$, velocity and acceleration etc.

We, however, first start with a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas which is a static equilibrium problem i.e. there are no macroscopic changes in time and there is a clear spatial density $d(x)$. This density may adjust itself. There is also the fixed potential $V(x)$. If $V(x)$ and $-\ln(d(x))$ are not essentially the same, we argue there must be special information (constraints etc) in the system to distinguish between the two. We note that average kinetic energy in the state problem is a constant including temperature multiplied by density. Thus we suggest that $-\ln(d(x)) = C V(x)$ to minimize information content.

We try to extend this idea to a Newtonian system, but a major difference there is that even though $V(x)$ is static, depending only depends on x , the particle depends on x and t . If one divides the x axis into equally spaced dx units then each is associated with a possibly different $dt(x)$. Thus we define function $(x) = dx/dt$. (We place dt in the denominator because we want the expression to be consistent with the time displacement generator d/dt .)

We next introduce information as $-\ln(d(x))$. The problem that arises is that even though one may move from one constant width dx to another for $V(x)$ in a uniform way i.e. using the translation generator d/dx , this cannot be done for the particle because $dt(x)$ changes within each x . Thus $-\ln(d(x))$ moves according to the generator d/dt we argue which is equivalent to $dx/dt \frac{d}{dx}$ i.e. a weighted average of d/dx which accounts for the different $dt(x)$ values. Then we suggest that: $d/dt (-\ln(d(x))) = C \frac{dV}{dx}$. We cannot use $V(x)$ as in the MB case because d/dt considers changes so there must be changes on the RHS as well. Alternatively one may argue that the LHS is a vector so the RHS must also be one. As a result one has: $dx/dt \frac{d}{dx} (-\ln(d(x))) = C \frac{dV}{dx}$ where $dx/dt = \text{function}(x)$. We argue that in equilibrium one should minimize information content. If one has two separate functions $-\ln(d(x))$ and $\text{function}(x)$ there must be some rules/constraints to distinguish the two. We do not see these and suggest that $\text{function}(x) = -\ln(d(x))$. Writing $\text{function}(x) = v(x)$ one has:

$v(x) \frac{dv(x)}{dx} = C \frac{dV}{dx}$ which is of the form of Newton's second law. Integrating leads to the conservation law: $.5v(x)v(x) - CV(x) = \text{constant}$. In this way each x point is associated with a

constant so one has removed information about x at each point by considering a sum of $.5v(x)v(x)$ and $-CV(x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Invariance, Information and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Factor? (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. Majernik, Vladimir; Richterek, Lukas (1997-12-01). "[Entropic uncertainty relations for the infinite well](#)". J. Phys. A. 30 (4): L49. [Bibcode:1997JPhA...30L..49M](#). [doi:10.1088/0305-4470/30/4/002](#). Retrieved 11 February 2016.